

CORRECTLY ORGANIZING HISTORY LESSONS USING INTERESTING GAME METHODS

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Annotation: *In recent years, the basis of the ongoing reforms in the system of continuing education in our country is the dissemination of best practices that can meet international educational standards, as well as practical work to achieve high efficiency in the educational process with less physical effort.*

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The most important and urgent task facing general secondary school teachers today is to increase students' interest in learning and broaden their horizons. To date, a number of measures have been taken to implement this work, which has laid the foundation for the success of educational effectiveness in general secondary schools. One of the important conditions for the effectiveness of the lesson is that the teacher and the students search for the truth together and the students actively participate in the whole lesson process. Of course, practice shows that new pedagogical technologies are available to teachers.

Nowadays, every science teacher is tasked with a comprehensive view of man, his place and role in society. To do this, the teacher must master new forms, means and methods of education, and at the same time try to create modern pedagogical technologies, choose new traditional, effective methods of personal development and be creative.

The social sciences, including history, taught in schools play an important role in educating a person who embodies noble qualities. At school, students learn the basics of the history of human society, their struggle against foreign invaders, their struggle for freedom and happiness, for a bright future. At the same time, history lessons help the student to understand the current socio-political processes.

As we know, history is one of the most ancient sciences. The science of history can be called a "mirror" of the future, and based on this mirror, any person, society,

nation can determine its own future. Today, it is not easy for Uzbekistan to become one of the developed countries. Therefore, in the process of teaching history, it is necessary to teach students to appreciate the present, not to repeat the mistakes of the past, to draw conclusions from the mistakes of the past. In addition, through the teaching of history at school, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of independent and creative thinking of students, the development of national consciousness and thinking, and most importantly, the upbringing of a spiritually mature person, a true patriot.

In order to carry out these tasks in the educational process, today's pedagogical staff must use new pedagogical technologies that are interesting and effective in every lesson.

We know that the basis of historical science is data. Completely remembering them can be a bit of a challenge for students (some low-achieving students). Such information depends on the fact that it will be remembered in the memory of students for a lifetime, different scenes, interesting game modes, crossword puzzles, group work, discussions.

The "ground to the subject" method

The goal: Before reinforcing the topic, prepare the students for the lesson.

We know that students can master the subject when the teacher explains it and by reading from the textbook. But this does not mean that all students in the class can master it. Because not all students have the same memory, the same way of thinking. Therefore, if lessons are organized for them through various games, scenes, debates, even the students who are not able to master the class well will not only gain an understanding of the topic, but also strengthen it. When reinforcing a topic covered during a lesson, it is important to first prepare the students for the lesson. A good lesson, a good mastery of the students, first of all, the teacher should attract the students, start the topic from scratch,

This method is used to prepare more students for the lesson, to repeat the previous topic and to prepare the ground for reinforcement. This method is advisable if it is done in grades 5-11. Groups are defined. Students should be divided into groups of 5-7 people. When dividing into groups, care should be taken to ensure that the forces of the groups are equal. Each group should be able to accommodate 2-3 students who are able to master well and students who are not able to master it well.

Each group should have a name of its own. To do this, the teacher asks the groups, "When you name a group, pay attention to the following?"

You name your group using words that evoke an event from within the topic covered, or words that make up one of the main content of the topic covered; Prepare with your group to explain why you put this name (1 minute is given).

After each group has been named, those groups should be asked why they gave that name.

After completing the above, students prepare a groundwork to reinforce the topic by giving students a brief overview of the topic covered. These groups can then be asked questions and assignments to reinforce the topic covered.

The "Summary-Tree Harvest" method

The goal: "Summary in a tree crop" is a playful way of analyzing and answering questions that lead to the main content of a topic. Through this playful method, the reader is able to draw the main conclusion of the topic and exchange ideas with each other to clarify the narrative of events.

Recommendations for application steps:

1. It should be used when reinforcing a more discussed topic.
2. This method is appropriate if done in grades 5-9.
3. In order to conduct the "Conclusion in a tree harvest" method, first of all, a tree is drawn on a poster or a blackboard, and simple questions that form the main content of the topic and problem-solving questions are written on the tree branches.

The main reason why simple questions are written is that you know that only if problematic questions are written can students with excellent grades answer, but low-achieving students may not be able to answer. That's why soda questions ensure the participation of all students in the class. This leads to competition among students.

4. After the questions are written on the tree branches in the above order, the students' answers are abbreviated and written in the "Answers" section of the tree. The answers are correct or slightly off the question, even if they are incorrect, they are written in the "Answers" section of the tree. The question may arise as to why incorrect or slightly off-topic answers are also recorded. The main reason for this is that students correct the student's error in the analysis process, and this process leads to controversy.

5. The answers in the "Answers" section of the tree are analyzed together with the students, and the most correct and optimal conclusion is written in the "Summary of Answers" section of the "Answers" section of the tree. This procedure continues until all questions have been answered.

6. The summary of the answers in the "Summary of Answers" section is analyzed together with the students, and the main conclusion of the most recent topic is written in the "Summary of the Final Topic" section of the tree. It can be seen that the main conclusion of the topic comes from the process of step-by-step analysis of the answers.

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